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ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES AND THE CONTRIBUTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS IN THEIR FORMATION

A.S. Aleksandrovich,

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor

T.I. Zimatkina,

Ph.D., Associate Professor

V.A. Labovich,

Grodno State Medical University,

Grodno

Annotation: In the course of the study, the regularities of the formation of environmentally conditioned oncology were studied. As a result of the study, analyzing the data on the influence of environmental factors in the formation of oncological diseases, it was concluded that it is necessary to develop educational work among the population by medical workers., which can significantly improve the detection of new cases of oncological morbidity.

Keywords: mortality, morbidity, oncological diseases

ОНКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ И ВКЛАД ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ В ИХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ

А.С. Александрович,

к.м.н., доц.

Т.И. Зиматкина,

к.б.н., доц.

В.А. Лабович,

Гродненский государственный медицинский университет,

г. Гродно

Аннотация: В процессе исследования изучены закономерности формирования экологически обусловленных

онкологий. В результате исследования, проанализировав данные о влиянии экологических факторов в формировании онкологических заболеваний, сделан вывод о необходимости развития просветительской работы среди населения медицинскими работниками., что сможет существенно улучшить выявление новых случаев онкологической заболеваемости.

Keywords: смертность, заболеваемость, онкологические заболевания

Relevance. Oncological diseases are one of the leading causes of death in the world, which by 2020 It claimed the lives of about 10 million people, or almost every sixth person who died. An environmental factor contributes significantly to the formation of these diseases: physical, chemical and biological carcinogens. The study of the mechanism of influence of environmental factors on carcinogenesis is the main focus of modern oncology [1-4].

The purpose of the work. The study of the regularities of the formation of environmentally conditioned oncologies.

Materials and methods of research. Analytical and comparative-evaluative research methods were used in the work.

Results and their discussion. Currently, oncological pathology is one of the most common and socially significant types of diseases. Cancers rank second in the world in terms of mortality. Every year, the trend towards an increase in the number of cases is progressing. Over the past 10 years [5-8], the indicator has grown by 40 %. This may indicate, on the one hand, the effectiveness of early diagnosis, on the other hand, a higher rate of spread of oncological diseases.

Environmental factors of the development of oncological diseases have always been on the list of the main ones.

It has been proven that the impact of adverse factors on the body affects the carcinogenesis of any type of tumors and changes in cellular structures. Atypical cells begin to grow, divide uncontrollably and form tumors.

Environmental factors that increase the risk of cancer include: exhaust gases, significant dustiness of the air in urban industrial areas,

radiation, prolonged contact with asbestos, nickel, arsenic, chromium, work in coal mines, passive smoking and others.

The assessment of the overall cancer risk due to environmental pollutants in developed countries is 8-9 %.

One of the main causes of lung cancer is air pollution. Some of the atmospheric pollutants that lead to cancer include benzpyrene, benzene, some metals and, to some extent, ozone.

The combustion products of automobile fuel are another problem of increased risk of cancer. These include organic compounds such as benzene, toluene, xylenes, acetylene, as well as nitrogen oxides and suspended microparticles of solids.

Cancer prevention by improving the environment may include the reduction (or elimination) of carcinogens in the production and human environment. For example, the closure of harmful industries, control of hazardous technologies, reduction of industrial emissions into the atmosphere, reduction of gas pollution, reduction of radiation load on the population. The main sources of atmospheric air pollution are enterprises of the metallurgical, coke-chemical, oil refining and aluminum industries, as well as thermal power plants (CHP) and road transport.

These productions are harmful. Carcinogens, which affect workers of harmful industries, are risk factors. Nickel, asbestos, sulfuric acid, epoxides, metals, arsenic, plastics and other chemicals affect the internal organs, where cells are transformed into malignant cells under the influence of carcinogens.

The link between the risk of cancer and the factors of harmful industries was first identified in 1950. The first occupational cancer was mesothelioma in asbestos workers. To date, it has been proven that most chemical compounds are carcinogenic substances.

For example, studies have shown that organic compounds such as benzidine and 2-naphthylamine cause occupational bladder cancer.

Stomach cancer is one of the main causes of significant morbidity and mortality in several professions related to coal and tin mining, metal processing, especially steel and iron, as well as the production of rubber products. There are also cases of bladder tumors in workers associated with the manufacture and use of various dyes.

There is an increased risk of lung cancer in workers who are exposed to hydrocarbon and chlorine-containing solvents, dyes, polyesters,

phenol-formaldehyde and polyurethane resins. Auramine dyes are used for dyeing leather, jute, tanned cotton and paints, as well as components of dyes in ball pastes, oils and waxes and carbon paper, they are also carcinogens.

The causative agent of leukemia is benzene and aromatic compounds, which are often used as a solvent and intermediate in the chemical and petroleum industries. Many studies report that benzene exposure causes non-lymphocytic and myelogenous leukemia. The recognition of asbestos dust as a carcinogen has been known since the 1950s. It has been proven that various forms of asbestos, such as chrysotile and amphibole, crocidolite, cause lung cancer and mesothelioma.

The risk of lung cancer is high for those who work in chromate-producing industries. Studies have shown that the risk is associated with hexavalent chromium compounds.

Various professions associated with contact with coal tar, coal gas extraction and iron smelting predispose to skin cancer, and can also affect the excretory and respiratory systems.

Ultraviolet radiation can also be conditionally attributed to environmental factors.

Melanoma is a type of oncology that can be obtained not only on the street, but also in a solarium. At risk are people with fair skin, hair and blue, green eyes. Factors of the development of near-illness under ultraviolet light provoke the development of bazalioma and squamous cell carcinoma. Prolonged exposure to beaches and outdoor pools, a history of sunburn, living in sunny regions is a health risk.

Conclusions. After analyzing the data on the influence of environmental factors in the formation of oncological diseases, I came to the conclusion that it is necessary to develop educational work among the population by medical workers. This will significantly reduce the increase in the detection of new cases of morbidity.

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